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**International Research Conference on Business,
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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2023**'s main theme is "***New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities***". In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2023** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

MUSIC BORN OF THE HEART

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ABSTRACT

Gaip Demesinov's compositional work is multifaceted. His bright multi-genre works are imbued with Karakalpak, Kazakh and Uzbek folk tunes.

His contribution to the treasury of Karakalpak music and his influence on the development of musical creativity of the country are extremely important.

INDEX TERMS

Composer, creativity, work, Karakalpak music, people, culture, symphonic music.

The path to a nationwide universal culture, described by all the best that has been created by the people, through the development of the cultures of socialist nations, through the full disclosure of the artistic representation of the world, embedded in the art of many peoples.

In modern music, the work of Gaipademesinov is one of the brightest phenomena of the Karakalpak musical art. G. Demesinov is a composer who came to the Karakalpak art in the early 70s of the XX century. He created many works in all musical genres, from the symphony to the song.

These are works for choir with symphony orchestra and arrangements of Karakalpak songs for voice and orchestra of folk instruments, where Demesinov worked for many years as orchestra conductor. Then a cycle of piano pieces for young people, chamber and instrumental works, romances and songs. Being an innovator in many genres of professional academic music, the composer has always strived to realize his ideas and ideas as much as possible. According to musicologist, member of the Union of Composers of Karakalpakstan D.Khudaibergenova, *"all his works are based on an original, creative thought, a deep national beginning"*. From an interview with the composer: "I was born in Karakalpakstan, in Kungrad.

I know the language, culture, traditions, customs of the people and I can't imagine myself outside of Karakalpak music. My first symphony is dedicated to the theme of the establishment of Soviet power in Karakalpakstan. The first part of it is called "Komsomol Members".

The second symphony "Bozatau" is about the historical past of the people, the ancient land of the Karakalpaks. The intonation, fret structure of the instrumental melodies of the Karakalpak people is used in piano concerts. This principle is preserved in the Prelude and Fugue for Symphony orchestra.

In addition, there are compositions of chamber-instrumental genre and vocal works. I consider it my duty to write music for the people on whose land I was born and grew up" from an interview with the composer ("I consider it my duty." interview with composer D. Dzhanabayeva–Soviet Karakalpakia)

After graduating from the conservatory, with his bright multi-genre works soaked in Karakalpak folk tunes, attracted the attention of the musical community and soon achieved the recognition of the people. In 1973 he became a member of the Union of Composers of Uzbekistan.

In order to develop modern musical creativity in Karakalpakstan, he worked hard: he created, taught, led an orchestra, processed and promoted folk music. Despite the fact that he lived a short life, he left a big mark on the history of the country's music.

Gaip Demesinov was born on February 9, 1942 in the Kungrad district of Karakalpakstan in a family of cattle breeders. His father Demesin and mother Kumisbike noticed the child's great interest in music already in early childhood, but they did not pay much attention to it and sent the child to an ordinary secondary school. In the school amateur circle, the boy learned to play the gidzhak.

One day, a violin teacher at a district music school, seeing how he plays the gidzhak, encourages him to study in a violin class at a music school in parallel, to which Gaip happily agrees. From this moment begins the professional activity of the future composer in the field of music, which he will not part with until the end of his days.

In 1958, Demesinov graduated from high school and began teaching music lessons at school. In 1960, after graduating from music school, he continued his studies in the violin class at the Nukus Music and Choreography College and graduated in 1964. After graduation, he is left as a violin teacher at this educational institution.

While working in high school and studying in Nukus, he is fond of composing and composes several works, these are: preludes for piano, violin, songs, sinfionetta for string orchestra, Concerto No. 1 for piano and orchestra and the "Karakalpak Symphony". And soon, in order to study composition professionally, in 1965 he entered the Tashkent State Conservatory in the class of Professor G. Mushel.

In 1971, Gaipdemesinov graduated with honors from the conservatory and received distribution to the Nukus Music College. There he teaches music theory. Among the early works written after graduating from higher education, there is a Sonata A-dur for violin and piano, Fantasy-prelude for piano, works a lot on treatments of Karakalpak folk songs. A remarkable event in those years was the review of the works of young composers. Initially, it was held in Uzbekistan, then in Almaty. The review was attended by representatives from the republics of Kazakhstan, Dagestan, Tatarstan, etc. The contest of young talents became a new impetus in the development of Demesinov's composing activity. Creative meetings, communication with colleagues enriched the spiritual world of the cosponsor.

In 1973, he was invited to work as concertmaster of the orchestra of the Karakalpak State Radio. From 1974 until the end of his life, Demesinov led this collective as a conductor.

Based on a combination of Western and Eastern musical traditions in his work, he achieved excellent results in composing music with a national flavor in different genres.

With all the variety of the composer's appeal to musical genres, symphonic music occupies a large place. The second Symphony, Prelude and Fugue for symphony orchestra, Concerto No. 2 and No. 3 – these are the works of the author that crown the creativity of the last decades. "Fruitfulness, maturity of thought, inexhaustible lyricism, breadth of scope, the ability to build a large-scale form, as required by the symphony genre - all this is perfectly mastered by the composer." Symphonic works occupy a large place in the work of Gaip Demesinov. Symphonic music attracts with its bright national themes and confident mastery of orchestral writing. Already his first symphony "Karakalpakskaya" is a serious professional composition, fresh in language, dynamic and harmonious in form.

Part I – "Unforgettable" begins with an Introduction. The dramatic sound conveys the dynamics of the revolutionary events taking place in Karakalpakstan. The lament of the violin and flute tells about the past of his people. A hungry life. People who do not know how to stand up for themselves and meekly accept life as it is. Sad folk melodies are used in this part. And suddenly quiet lyrical melodies are replaced by rhythmic ones resembling the trampling of horses.

The rapidly increasing noise of the music reaches its highest point. This is the beginning of the struggle of the people. People's consciousness has awakened. The music then increases, then suddenly drops sharply: these are uprisings, riots (uprisings in which the people sometimes win, then suffer defeat. The part ends solemnly and victoriously.

Part II – lyrical "On the bank of the Amu Darya". It is like a sketch of the rich nature of the native land. In the second part, calm lyrical music sounds already. The full-flowing Amu Darya, beautiful nature rises before my eyes. Freedom. Peaceful life. This part is melodious, filled with transparent sound, creating a state of contemplation and peace.

The third part of "Komsomolets" is dedicated to modern youth and their successes. In the III part of the symphony there is live fast music. These are young people going to All-Union construction sites. There is a construction of a new life everywhere. The lively character of this part corresponds to the cheerful emotional tone inherent in Soviet youth.

The music of the symphony is deeply national, permeated with the intonations of Karakalpak folk melodies, the author managed to convincingly express the program laid down in the work by means of music.

His music covers the whole soul, leaves a deep trace. In all the composer's works, several themes develop at once. The sounds seem to enter into an argument, dance. Therefore, probably, the performance of G. Demesinov's music requires special skill, concepts.

A significant place in the composer's work is occupied by piano works, represented mainly by compositions of small form.

"In his piano compositions, contemporary in style, Gaipdemesinov reflected the atmosphere of his surrounding life, the events of multifaceted reality. At the same time, his work is inextricably linked with the traditions of the musical art of the Karakalpak people, which has its roots in the depths of centuries. The composer deeply and organically felt the national flavor of native songs and instrumental tunes. His musical speech is close to the authentic Karakalpak melodic, fret, rhythmic turn, obeying the individual style of the composer"

Piano works are characterized by brightness, imagery, concreteness. They are distinguished by clarity, accessibility of content and form. Written with an understanding of the specific capabilities of the instrument, the composer's texturally comfortable piano works illustrate a deep insight into the nature of the Karakalpak national melos, introduce to folk traditions.

According to the style and dominant content, piano compositions can be characterized as lyric-dramatic. The composer avoids excessive expression, emotional relaxation. In his works, he asserts realism as an aesthetic and moral-ethical principle and on this basis develops the traditions of classical music, implements his own searches in the field of artistic imagery and musical expressiveness.

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